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Second report on biobank activities

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D8.6

WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level

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2 Glossary

2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl phthalate	5OH-MEPH
2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl phthalate	5oxo-MEHP
6-OH-Mono-propyl-heptyl phthalate	OH-MiDP
7-Carboxy-(mono-methylheptyl) phthalate	cx-MiNP
7-OH-(Mono-methyl-octyl) phthalate	OH-MiNP
Bisphenol A, S, F	BPA, S, F
cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate-mono-(7-carboxylate-4-methyl)heptyl ester	cx-MINCH
cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate-mono-(7-hydroxy-4-methyl)octyl ester	OH-MINCH
cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate-mono-(7-oxo-4-methyl)octyl ester	oxo-MINCH
Di(2-propylheptyl) phthalate	DPHP
Di-isononyl phthalate	DINP
Di-isononylcyclohexane 1,2-dicarboxylate	DINCH
Mono(2,7-methyl-7-carboxy-heptyl) phthalate	cx-MiDP
Mono(2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) phthalate	5cx-MEPP
monobenzyl phthalate	MBzP
Mono-cyclo-hexyl phthalate	MCHP
monoethyl phthalate	MEP
monoethylhexyl phthalate	MEHP
monoisobutyl phthalate	MiBP
mono-n-butyl phthalate	MnBP
Mono-n-octyl phthalate	MnOP
Mono-n-pentyl phthalate	MnPeP
Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons	PAH
Polyvinyl chloride	PVC

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3 Abstract/Summary

Task 8.2 investigates data sources and gaps for the purpose of evaluating time trends in chemical exposure across Europe. Hence the aim is to collect exposure data covering three time points, two age groups and four geographical regions.

For the first time point literature data will be used. For the second time point it was decided to make use of the DEMOCOPHES biobank samples and for the third time point data generated by the Task 8.1 aligned studies will be utilised.

This report focuses on the data collection strategy for new analyses in the DEMOCOPHES biobank samples, the pre-set of the conditions and the alignment with Task 8.1 aligned studies.

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4 Introduction

The aim of Work Package 8 (WP8) is to collect biomonitoring data across Europe in order to determine exposure to the HBM4EU priority list of chemicals either in the general population or via an occupational setting. Three strategies were proposed. Firstly, to align ongoing and new studies in partner countries and collect new samples (both for population and occupational exposures) in a harmonised way to achieve comparable exposure data, secondly, to access biobank samples for retrospective analysis of chemical exposure, and lastly to collate HBM data which has already been collected and/or published. The Human Biomonitoring data collected will serve different purposes, including that to determine status and trends of chemical exposure across Europe, which is the aim of Task 8.2. The aim of this report is to provide an update of the work performed in Task 8.2.

For the time trend analyses in Task 8.2, three time-points will be assessed: 2006-2010, 2011-2013 and 2014-2019. The aim is to include two age-groups (children and adult women) and the four European geographical areas (north, south, east, west), provided data is available. Time-trends will be assessed for DINCH, bisphenols, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), organophosphate (OP) flame retardants, phthalates and cadmium, all included in the HBM4EU first priority list of substances.

For the first time point we suggest using published exposure data gathered from literature and by the chemical group leaders. For the second time point we will perform new analyses in the DEMOCOPHES biobank samples, collected in 2011-2012. For the third time point we will rely on new HBM data collected in Task 8.1 (alignment of studies).

This is the second progress report for Task 8.2.

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5 Task 8.2 data collection strategy

5.1 Description of work

The overall aim of Task 8.2 is to derive time-trend data for HMB4EU prioritised chemicals, i.e. DINCH, bisphenols (BPA, BPS), PAH, certain OP flame retardants, phthalates and cadmium, in each of four geographical regions, and for two age groups as described below. Three time-points will be assessed using appropriate available data.

Task 8.2 data base builds on information collected by Task 7.1 questionnaires and the resulting database, scoping documents for the first round of prioritised substances which were prepared by the chemical group leaders, scientific literature, and new HBM analyses.

New chemical analyses will be performed on some of the DEMOCOPHES biobank samples (collected 2011-2012) and those collected in Task 8.1 aligned studies (2014-2020).

New analyses of the biobank samples will be undertaken to provide retrospective exposure information for a set of chemicals to be compared with data collected in women and children 2014-2019 for the same set of chemicals, and for time-trend analysis.

All new analyses should be carried out at laboratories that have successfully passed the quality assurance program established by WP9. The first list of approved laboratories was presented in August 2019 and is continuously updated by WP9.

The selection of chemicals to be analysed in the DEMOCOPHES biobank samples is based on the selection of chemicals to be analysed in Task 8.1 to facilitate comparison between the two. Since the DEMOCOPHES biobank consists of urine samples, only urine metabolites can be harmonised with the Task 8.1 studies, and since only mothers and their children were included in the DEMOCOPHES study, those are the population groups that can be compared with Task 8.1 population groups.

The number of data points needed for each time point in the trend analyses is based on statistical considerations and data availability. Since data is rather scarce it was decided to calculate descriptive statistics of aggregated data from each time point and strata. Time trends will be analysed in collaboration with WP10 Statistical Working Group and will include considering how the results between different countries and time trends can be compared.

Partners are committed to sharing their co-funded exposure data and accompanying variables at the individual or aggregated level in a HBM4EU harmonized format prescribed by WP10. All datasets used for research under HBM4EU must be accessible by sharing metadata (i.e. general information about the dataset, not actual data) ideally as first proposed via IPCHEM and be accessible to all IPCHEM user groups, however due to GDPR issues this requires further consideration. This is being carried out in WP10 (Lead VITO).

Ethical approvals of the studies as well as the permission to transfer the measurement data for statistical analysis at EU level should be made available to the project coordinator before implementation.

5.1.1 Strategy for exchange of samples and data

A strategy for exchange of samples was developed in collaboration with Task 7.4 (Strategy and SOPs for human sample exchange, including ethical demands. Deliverable Report D 7.2, revised version 18 June, 2019). The exchange of samples within Tasks 8.2 shall follow that strategy.

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5.1.2 Time points for time trend analysis

Data for three time points will be investigated and collected.

1. 2006-2010: Based on Task 7.1 questionnaires and the resulting database, scoping documents for the first round of prioritised substances, prepared by the Chemical Group Leaders, and scientific literature reviews, aggregated (or single) data
2. 2011-2012: Based on new HBM analyses of DEMOCOPHES urine samples from biobank material
3. 2014-2019/20: Based on new HBM analyses/results obtained in Task 8.1 aligned studies

5.1.3 Age groups

Task 8.2 aims for two age categories to be covered, in alignment with two of the age groups included in the Task 8.1 alignment studies.

1. Children 6-11 years
2. Women 20-45 years (to be compared with the aligned study women of 20-39 years)

5.1.4 European geographical regions

Europe was divided into 4 geographical regions based on the report D 8.1: A strategy to collect EU wide HBM data. The aim is to cover all four regions.

1. North: Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Iceland, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Sweden, UK
2. South: Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain
3. East: Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Slovakia
4. West: Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Switzerland

5.1.5 Prioritised substances and target groups

The compounds of interest are selected based on the first HBM4EU list of priority chemicals, covered by the analytical quality assurance program established by WP9, and in alignment with the compounds to be analysed in Task 8.1 (Table 1). For budgetary reasons the analyses may have to be restricted to the target groups that were selected in Task 8.1 aligned studies for comparison of results. However, some partners have declared they will analyse an extended list of metabolites than those listed in Table 1.

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Table 1: Proposed prioritised chemicals and target groups planned to be analysed in the DEMOCOPHES biobank urine samples in alignment with task 8.1 study.

Chemical compounds	Metabolites	Reported in DEMOCOPHES study	Target group
DINCH	OH-MINCH, cx-MINCH		Children
BPA		Already analysed in 6 countries (Covaci et al 2015)*. Analyse in additional countries?	Women
BPS			Women
BPF	<i>To be decided when approved laboratories have been identified</i>		Women
PAH	1-hydroxynaphthalene, 2-hydroxynaphthalene, 1-hydroxypyrene		Women
Organophosphate flame retardants	<i>To be decided</i>		Children
Phthalates	MEHP, 5OH-MEHP, 5oxo-MEHP, 5cx-MEPP, MEP, MBzP, MiBP, MnBP, MCHP, MnPeP, MnOP, OH-MiNP, cx-MiNP, OH-MiDP, cx-MiDP	MEHP, 5OH-MEPH, 5oxo-MEHP, MEP, MBzP, MnBP, MiBP** ***	Children
Cadmium		Already analysed	Women

* Belgium, Denmark, Luxembourg, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden

**Denmark has already analysed the full suggested set of metabolites, except one

*** Spain can provide data on all full set of phthalates metabolites analysed by a WP9 reference lab.

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6 Results

6.1 New analyses in the DEMOCOPHES biobank

Biobank samples can be analysed for the purpose of achieving retrospective information on exposure levels. Most human biobank materials were not collected for the purpose of analysing environmental or product chemicals, instead small volumes of human matrices are collected for specific research questions. We investigated possible biobank materials available for retrospective analyses for time trend analyses for the first two time points (2006-2010, 2011-2012), for analyses of prioritised chemicals in urine (information presented in First report on biobank activities, D8.2).

For financial and practical reasons, it was decided to focus on one biobank, the DEMOCOPHES biobank. The DEMOCOPHES study is well defined and harmonised at the European level. It fit the purpose of gaining exposure data for time trend analyses, for one time point in the selected time frame (2011-2012), and for two age groups (6-11 and women 20-45 years; table 2). Several substances have already been analysed in the samples and the overall results reported. Already published data from the DEMOCOPHES study includes seven phthalate metabolites, BPA (subset of countries) and Cd (Den Hond et al 2015; Covaci et al 2015). We suggest analysing metabolites of interest in both children and their mothers, as well as other metabolites in the same urine samples, as long as analytical quality can be evaluated and it fits the budget allocated since the DEMOCOPHES biobank material has to be discarded in 2021 at the latest. Thus, the use of this high-quality material represents cost and effort efficiencies.

Currently, ten partners have announced interest in performing new analyses in their DEMOCOPHES biobank urine samples (Table 2).

Table 2: DEMOCOPHES biobank. Countries and partners that have announced interest in new analyses of biobank urine samples, and maximum number of samples available for children and their mothers.

Region	Country/partner	Maximum No. of samples available	Children	Women
North	Denmark/UCPH	240	120	120
	Sweden/SEPA/KI	194	97	97
South	Cyprus/ MOH-CY	120	60*	60*
	Slovenia/JSI	240	120	120
East	Spain/ISCIII	240	120	120
	Czech Republic/MU/SZU-CZ	240	120	120
West	Poland/NIOM	218	109	109
	Belgium/VITO	236	118	118
	Germany/UBA	227	113	114**
	Luxembourg/LNS	120	60	60

*waiting for ethical approval

**PAHs only

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